

“METHODODOLOGICAL BASIS FOR RESEARCH ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF HEALTH ORIENTATION IN ADOLESCENT STUDENTS”

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Annotation: Health is defined as the ability of a person to have their own personality, “self-awareness”, to fully and harmoniously join the Society of people. In our opinion, as a sense of self-awareness develops in adolescence, the perception that their own health is the main criterion for the path to personal development also provides the basis for saying that compliance with the requirements of society and filling the xiss of having a place in oneself is also significant.

Аннотация: Здоровье определяется как наличие у человека собственной личности, «самореализации», полная и гармоничная интеграция людей в общество. Мы думаем, что по мере того, как чувство собственного достоинства развивается в подростковом возрасте, их восприятие того, что их собственное здоровье является основным критерием на пути личностного развития, также имеет значение для удовлетворения требований общества и чувства собственного достоинства.

Key words: Adolescence, Health, individual health, communication, spiritual, environmental, physical.

Ключевые слова: подростковый возраст, здоровье, индивидуальное здоровье, общение, духовное, экологическое, физическое.

Introduction.

"Health" is an extremely relevant issue, and the formation of an attitude to health is of great importance in all aspects, both in social life and in scientific research. Despite the small number of scientific studies of the issue of health and the mechanisms affecting it, the disclosure of this concept has been described in scientific research. When describing the concept of a health-oriented personality orientation, we can interpret it as a combination of the concepts of "person orientation" and "health".

According to Aizmanov R.I., the holistic concept of health emphasizes the important role of the individual in maintaining health, forming a unity of

spiritual-psychological and material-physical components. In his opinion, the author notes that there are several options for determining health, focusing on the mental, somatic, spiritual, ecological and social components of health.

1. individual health - the natural state of the body, expressed in the absence of pathological changes, optimal interaction with the environment and the consistency of all functions (G.Z. Demchinkova, N.L. Polonsky).

2. A harmonious combination of the structural and functional data of the organism, providing the organism with optimal vital activity, as well as full-fledged labor activity.

3. Individual health - a harmonious unity of all possible metabolic processes in the organism, which creates conditions for the optimal functioning of all systems and subsystems of the organism (A.D. Ado).

4. Health is the biological, psychological functions of a person during the maximum duration of his active life, his working capacity and social activity (V.P. Kaznacheev).

5. V. P. Kaznacheev: "Health is the process of maintaining and developing biological, physiological and psychological functions, optimal working capacity and social activity during the maximum duration of a person's life" [58]. In our opinion, the formation of health in adolescents is also explained by ensuring their biological, psychological, and social stability in all aspects.

According to A.N. Leontiev, the individual is created by social relations that participate in his objective activity, and the "personality of the individual" is produced. The individual is primarily formed in society, and a person, endowed with natural properties and abilities, develops only as a subject of social relations. Since personal development is assessed as a process of interaction of many of our activities, a person acts as a set of hierarchical relations of activity. A. N. Leontiev, studying the identity of the individual in his research, states that activity is "connected" with the states of the body. The author recognizes that this hierarchy of activities has a developmental character, and they constitute the core of the individual.

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